

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

APPLICATION OF BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY FOR MANAGEMENT OF NETWORKS WITH DISTRIBUTED GENERATION

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ABSTRACT

Current study explored the application of blockchain technology and smart contracts for management of electrical networks that combines renewable energy sources and gas turbine units. Also, study proposes the algorithm of adaptation of smart contracts to automate electricity trading agreements, balance power capacities, and data protection. Moreover, a model of subnetwork was created that includes renewable sources of energy, a gas turbine power plant, and industrial and residential consumers. The simulation of isolated and parallel operation modes has been conducted.

The results of the current study demonstrated an effectiveness of the algorithm in providing stability, fulfillment of power restriction and enhancement of energy system flexibility. This demonstrates the feasibility of implementation of the proposed approach in order to support the sustainable development of decentralized energy markets.

Keywords: smart contract, wind and solar energy, power management and distribution, blockchain, algorithm, smart contract.

INTRODUCTION

The Interconnected Power System of Ukraine undergoes significant changes that aimed to integrate with the European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity (ENTSO-E). This integration is an important contribution to the stability and reliability of Ukraine’s energy system, as well as a push off for the development of the electricity market in Ukraine. At this background, the development of smart grids gains significant importance as it enables much more efficient management of energy resources and loss optimization, as well as an improvement of electricity supply reliability. A blockchain technology is one of the key tools that are able to facilitate the development of smart grids.

Blockchain provides a decentralized, transparent, and secure data management across various sectors (those aspects are crucial for modern energy systems) and the usage of blockchain-based smart contracts allow to explore new opportunities for automatization and optimization of the management of energy system. Current approach allows to advance the automatization of power distribution within the energy system, thereby increasing the security and reliability of transactions within the network, as well as to enhance the trust to a transparent and decentralized energy market.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In current years, blockchain technology has been actively studied for its usage in the energy sector, mainly within the concepts of “smart” energy systems and decentralized markets. Smart contracts that are implemented based blockchain platforms, enable the automatization of electricity trading processes, quotation among market participants, and the management of distributed energy resources [1, 2]. It provides transparency and trust without the involvement of intermediaries. Smart contracts can optimize the usage of distributed energy sources such as solar panels or wind turbines by taking into account the generation of fluctuations and real-time dynamic pricing [3]. Moreover, blockchain helps to verify the origin of “green” energy and guarantees fulfillment of the contract [4]. However, specific challenges arise during the integration of smart contracts with traditional generators (such as gas turbine units (GTUs)). Unlike renewable energy sources (RES), GTUs operate in a fixed mode and poorly adapt to the dynamic conditions of flexible contracts, reducing the potential of automatization [5]. Also, another limitation is a scalability of blockchain network: large data volumes and transactions (that is typical for energy systems) causes the delay in the processing.

In the network with a high percentage of RES, an additional complexity is related to unstable generation of electricity. Smart contracts require an accurate production forecasting and real-time management of demand and supply balance, which is challenging due to significant variability in solar and wind generation [6]. Furthermore, integration of distributed generators into a single platform raises legal and regulatory issues, and the transparency of blockchain ledgers conflicts with the requirements of consumer personal data protection [7]. Thus, the blockchain and smart contracts are able to enhance the efficiency and transparency of energy markets, however, their successful application alongside traditional generators (such as GTUs and RES) requires to solve issues related to scalability, cybersecurity and regulatory integration.

The aim of the current study is to adapt smart contracts for electrical networks that combine RES and

traditional generation, specifically GTUs. Study involves the development and testing of mechanisms that provide:

- automatic formation and execution of contracts for electricity trading;
- flexible response to the instability of RES generation;
- compatibility with the operating modes of traditional generators (GTUs);
- protection of personal data and high cybersecurity resilience.

DISCUSSION

Current study selected a fragment of power system, that consists of consumers, wind (WPP), solar (SPP), and GTU, as well as transmission lines connected to the external power system (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Fragment of power system

The model of the network fragment is simplified in order to optimize the operation of smart contracts within testing networks and contains a sequential description of the main parameters of generation with which the smart contract interacts, and the description of power consumption by residential and industrial consumers. The function of distribution substation is related to equal distribution of generation among all consumers, transfer of the excess of generation to external grid, and the supply of electricity from the external grid on time when an internal generation is insufficient.

The maximum transfer capacity to/from the external grid is limited to 20 MVA during off-peak hours and 10 MVA during peak hours (6pm-9pm). These restrictions simulate parallel operation with other energy power systems.

The SPP acts as the RES with the highest peak capacity. Its generation depends on the solar emission that results in the schedule generation with peak values during the daytime. The maximum generation capacity is 50 MVA, with peak generation during day time and absence of generation at night time. Weather conditions, especially cloudiness, can significantly reduce generation. The WPP provides a stable generation that depends on the wind conditions, with generation capacity

starting from 25 MVA. Generation also depends on the wind fluctuations.

The industrial consumer is a big electricity consumer, with a consumption profile depending on production processes. Characteristics include high consumption during work hours, with peaks reaching up to 25 MVA. The possibility of consumption optimization during peak load hours is essential in order to maintain network stability. Residential consumers have typical consumption profiles with morning and evening peaks. Peak power consumption can reach up to 90 MVA in the morning and in the evening times. A big number of consumers can create a significant load during peak hours.

GTU is used in order to cover power deficits within the part of the network with its maximum generation capacity of 20 MVA. It operates when the consumption exceeds generation and it is impossible to cover the deficit from the external grid. Rapid start-up is possible for immediate coverage of the deficit.

In the current study, we developed an algorithm for the smart contract operation that describes the sequence of calculations performed on the input data, as well as the operation of some auxiliary functions that provide data input and output for the smart contract algorithm. The block diagram of the algorithm is presented on Figure 2.

The analysis of the most common blockchain platforms [8] showed the advisability of using Ethereum, due to the fact that it is the most widespread and well-supported platform for smart contracts, with a large ecosystem and a vast number of developers ensuring reliability and ongoing support. The smart contract was developed using the Solidity programming language [9] in the Remix IDE environment [10]. A web application in the form of an HTML file was created in order to interact with the smart contract that runs in a browser supporting Web3.

Three operating modes of the studied power system fragment were assessed: isolated mode and parallel operation mode with the external power system (with power surplus and deficit). Figure 3 presents daily power distribution graphs for the studied energy system, peak coverage, interaction with the external network, generation and consumption limits, and their balance.

Figure 3. Simulation results

Our results demonstrate that throughout the day, the generation from SPP and WPP remains stable, while the consumption rate by residential and industrial sectors shows characteristic peak values. Interaction with the external grid provides the necessary balance during periods when internal generation is insufficient.

The algorithm operates correctly under different modes of the power system fragment, properly distributing power and ensuring compliance with established consumption and generation power limits, which confirms the effectiveness of the proposed approach and the developed smart contract algorithm.

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, smart contracts were adapted for electrical networks combining RES and GTUs. Developed smart contract algorithm enables:

- To automatically make and execute electricity trading agreements between network participants;

- To flexibly response to fluctuations in renewable energy generation via usage of the forecast data and the dynamic adjustment of contract parameters;

- To consider technical characteristics of GTU operation in order to ensure a correct power balance in a hybrid energy systems;

- To guarantee the protection of confidential data and compliance with regulatory requirements through built-in access control and encryption mechanisms.

The modeling in the current study demonstrated that the application of adapted smart contracts in hybrid networks improves the efficiency of operational processes, reduces the time spent on initiation of agreement, and contributes to more stable energy system operation.

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